

Polyfunctionality and Equilibrium Selectivity Coefficient of Ion-exchange System. Part II—Interaction of Some Monovalent Ions with H-Co(pn)₃-Bentonite and Na-Co(pn)₃-Bentonite

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The extent to which the polyfunctional character of bentonite influences the ion exchange behaviour of Co(pn)₃³⁺ on and from H⁺ and Na⁺ forms of bentonite against different monovalent inorganic ions has been investigated at 25°. The sequence of equilibrium selectivity coefficients i.e., Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < NH₄⁺ < Rb⁺ < Cs⁺ for the exchange of Co(pn)₃³⁺ from H-Co(pn)₃-bentonite and Na-Co(pn)₃-bentonite remains unaltered in both the systems. However, there are significant differences in the values of the selectivity coefficients for each desorbing ion between the two clay systems. The experimental results would, therefore, suggest that bentonite behaves as a strong cation exchanger although it shows polyfunctional properties. The plot of log (selectivity coefficient) vs the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel parameter, a° , yields linear curves. This implies that in such a process of exchange of Co(pn)₃³⁺ by monovalent ions, the electrostatic attraction between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups is the determining factor and the parameter a° of the ions may be used to correlate the relative affinities of the ions for the mineral.

STUDIES on the electrochemical nature of clay minerals have long been an interesting field of research. The neutralisation curves of these polyacids were found to give inflexions which indicated weak acidic characteristics^{1,2}. The inflexions obtained during the titration of clay acids were explained on the concepts of crystallinity³ and the layer lattice structure⁴ which assumed the existence of exchange spots with different bonding energies. The exchange sites originate both from isomorphous substitution in the tetrahedral or octahedral layer of the crystal lattice and from broken bonds on the edges of the crystal, which may explain part of the polyfunctional character of clays as reflected in their pH titration curves. In the present communication *tris* 1,2 propylene diamine Co(III) i.e. Co(pn)₃³⁺ was exchanged onto H-bentonite (pH ≈ 2.6) and Na-bentonite (pH ≈ 7.0) and the release of Co(pn)₃³⁺ from the clay matrices by a number of monovalent ions was studied with a view to investigate the relative strength of binding of Co(pn)₃³⁺ with the clays vis-a-vis polyfunctional behaviour of bentonite.

Experimental

The bentonite was procured from Evans Medical Ltd., Liverpool, England and <2.0 μm particle size fraction was used in the present investigation. It was converted into the H⁺ and Na⁺ forms by appropriate resin treatment (Dowex 50W × 8 and Dowex 2 × 8). The methods adopted to study the sorption of Co(pn)₃Cl₃ onto H-bentonite and Na-bentonite and their subsequent desorption from

the respective clay matrices by monovalent ions were similar to those reported earlier⁵. The percentages (w/v) of clay suspensions used for the release of Co(pn)₃³⁺ from the clay-complexes were 1.493 and 1.334 for H-Co(pn)₃-bentonite and Na-Co(pn)₃-bentonite respectively.

Results and Discussion

According to the theory of Eisenman⁶, the equilibrium selectivity order of a polymer is determined by the changing field strength of the fixed exchange sites i.e. by the charge and the polarizing power of the cation and the polarizability of the fixed anionic sites and that of the solvent medium. Thus the selectivity sequences conform to the Lyotrope series in the strong acid exchangers while the opposite effect is noted in weak acid exchangers because they have high and low anionic field strengths respectively. It is, therefore, reasonable to expect that a polyfunctional exchanger i.e. one having exchange sites with a range of anionic field strengths, should show intermediate selectivity sequences depending on the relative proportion of strong to weak exchange sites.

The maximum sorption capacities of Co(pn)₃³⁺ onto H-bentonite (pH ≈ 2.6) and Na-bentonite (pH ≈ 7.0) correspond to 83 m.e/100 g and 96 m.e/100 g respectively. The uptake at low pH possibly corresponds to exchange due to isomorphous lattice replacement while the higher exchange at pH 7.0 could be due to the additional sorption at the edges primarily caused by Si-O and Al-O

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{pn})_3$ -bentonite by monovalent ions.

sites. It is apparent that during the interaction of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ with H-bentonite only the negatively charged flat surfaces of the electrical double layer is available for the sorption of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ whereas the positive double layer on the edges of the clay⁷ at low pH remains ineffective for exchange. But the polarity of the double layer at the edges of the crystal lattice becomes negative at higher pH and hence the exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ at the edges of the clay can take place in Na-bentonite.

The release of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ from H- $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3$ -bentonite and Na- $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3$ -bentonite by monovalent ions is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The selectivity coefficients of the desorbing ions have been calculated as in our previous paper⁵ and is recorded in Table 1. As the values of the activity coefficients of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ are not available in the literature, concentrations of the ions have been used in calculating

selectivity coefficients and the values, therefore, are less accurate. The thermodynamic equilibrium constants of the exchange reactions except in the cases of Li^+ and Na^+ have been evaluated from the linear plot of the experimental results (Fig. 3) by use of the following equation of Kielland^{8*}. Gibbs free energy change at 25° has been computed from the relation $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln k$. Any differences in selectivity of the exchanging ions should be reflected in the thermodynamic equilibrium constant and standard Gibbs free energy change. The results are shown in Table 1.

As mentioned earlier, the $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ saturation at pH 7.0 is found to be 96 m.e./100 g while at pH 2.5 it is 83 m.e./100 g. If this excess exchange with pH is the consequence of greater dissociation of weak acid exchange sites having higher anionic field strengths, this should be reflected in the selectivity

where the bar refers to the clay phase.

$$\log K = \log k + C[n \cdot 2\bar{x}_B + (n - m)\bar{x}_B^2]$$

where K = Selectivity coefficient,

k = thermodynamic equilibrium constant,

\bar{x}_B = equivalent ionic fraction of B in the exchanger phase and

C = a constant.

Fig. 2. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_2^{2+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{pn})_2$ -bentonite by monovalent ions.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log(\text{Selectivity Coefficient})$ against $[n-2nx_B + (n-m)x_B^2]$ in the desorption of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_2^{2+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{pn})_2$ -bentonite (●) and $\text{Na-Co}(\text{pn})_2$ -bentonite (○) by monovalent ions.

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolyte (M)	Selectivity Coefficient		Equilibrium Constant		ΔG° cal/mole	
		(H-B)	(Na-B)	(H-B)	(Na-B)	(H-B)	(Na-B)
LiCl	0.10	0.075	0.095	—	—	—	—
	0.15	0.079	0.108	—	—	—	—
	0.20	0.089	0.110	—	—	—	—
	0.25	0.093	0.110	—	—	—	—
NaCl	0.10	0.088	0.161	—	—	—	—
	0.15	0.101	0.135	—	—	—	—
	0.20	0.112	0.142	—	—	—	—
	0.25	0.122	0.146	—	—	—	—
KCl	0.10	0.119	0.194	0.275	0.320	763	673
	0.15	0.143	0.206	—	—	—	—
	0.20	0.158	0.227	—	—	—	—
	0.25	0.168	0.241	—	—	—	—
NH_4Cl	0.10	0.152	0.258	0.355	0.352	613	618
	0.15	0.176	0.272	—	—	—	—
	0.20	0.192	0.290	—	—	—	—
	0.25	0.203	0.300	—	—	—	—
RbCl	0.05	0.239	0.408	—	—	—	—
	0.075	0.275	0.451	0.476	0.554	439	349
	0.10	0.295	0.463	—	—	—	—
	0.15	0.349	0.498	—	—	—	—
	0.20	0.381	0.510	—	—	—	—
CsCl	0.05	0.852	1.177	—	—	—	—
	0.075	0.894	1.170	—	—	—	—
	0.10	0.925	1.195	0.933	1.222	41	-119
	0.15	0.914	1.129	—	—	—	—

behaviour. So it is reasonable to expect that there would either be a decrease in selectivity difference within the Lyotrope series $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$ or a reversal of selectivity sequences depending on the magnitude of the anionic field strengths and the relative proportion of strong to weak acid exchange sites. From Table 1 it can be observed that the equilibrium selectivity coefficients for a given alkali metal ion gradually increase with its proportion in the clay phase. This behaviour is expected, as clays have potentially variable exchange sites. It is interesting to note that the percentage of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ release from Na-Co(pn)₃-bentonite is always higher than that from H-Co(pn)₃-bentonite by each monovalent ion, which shows that $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ ions are less strongly held in Na-bentonite than in H-bentonite. This is also reflected in the comparatively higher values of the selectivity coefficients and equilibrium constants in Na-bentonite system. Table 1 shows that the order of the equilibrium selectivity coefficients of the monovalent ions $\text{Cs} > \text{Rb} > \text{NH}_4 > \text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$ remains unchanged in both the systems. Nevertheless, there are significant differences in selectivity coefficient values for each desorbing ion in H-Co(pn)₃-bentonite and Na-Co(pn)₃-bentonite systems. This is probably due to the fact that the proportion of the exchange sites at the flat surfaces and at the edges of the bentonite crystal lattice is not appropriate enough to show a difference in the relative position in the sequence of the Hofmeister series. Therefore, it can be concluded that as the exchange sequence of the monovalent ions obey the Hofmeister series, the bentonite behaves as a strong cation exchanger although the clay shows polyfunctional characteristics.

An attempt has been made here to correlate the relative affinities of the monovalent ions for the mineral surface with some other properties of the ions, viz., hydrated ionic radius⁹ and the reciprocal of the Debye Hückel parameter $a^{\circ 10}$ i.e. the distance of closest approach between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups. From Fig. 4 it can be noticed that a sharp break appears in the curve of log (selectivity coefficients) vs hydrated ionic radii while the plot of log (selectivity coefficients) against $\frac{1}{a^{\circ}}$ is linear. The latter plot follows from the simple electrostatic ion exchange model of Pauley¹¹ according to which the Coulombic forces are the main ones acting between the charged exchanger's surface and the counter ions. Pauley predicted standard free energies of exchange by determining the work necessary to remove each of the two types of cations involved from the distance of closest approach to infinity, against the Coulombic forces

Fig. 4. Correlation of selectivity coefficient with hydrated ionic radius and the Debye Hückel parameter a° in the exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ from H-Co(pn)₃-bentonite (●) and Na-Co(pn)₃-bentonite (○).

acting between the cation and the exchanger. The experimental results obtained here clearly indicate that in such a process of exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{pn})_3^{3+}$ by the monovalent ions, the a° is a better parameter than hydrated ionic radius to correlate the selectivities of the ions for bentonite surface.

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